

paper Chain

Guidelines for the implementation of
the Circular Economy models.

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New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

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0 Executive Summary

The present Document **D7.3 “Guidelines for the implementation of the Circular Economy models”** document has been elaborated for project paperChain, within the EU Horizon 2020 framework, under the grant agreement No. 730305. It aims to summarize the conclusions obtained in the Task 7.3 “Management Guidelines”, and tries to provide a valuable document for an early guiding for the implementation and replicability of the 5 Circular Economy Models proposed at PAPERCHAIN solution for the Construction, Transport and Chemical Sectors:

CC1 Construction manufacturing:

- a) Filler aggregate in pre-cast Concrete
- b) Fillers and fine aggregates in asphalt pavements

CC2 transport Infrastructures: Road Sector Hydraulic Road Binder applications

CC3 transport Infrastructures Railway Sector: Slope stabilization with Gabion wall construction

CC4 Chemical industry: bioethanol and Ethyl Chloride alternative production.

CC5 Mining Industry: mining waste sealing layer for mine reclamation.

Circularity refers to the circular flow and efficient use and reuse of resources, materials, and products. **PAPERCHAIN 5 new Circular Economy Models** represent sustainable green growth, moving from a consumption and disposal-based linear model to a system that extends the life of products and materials and minimises waste. The circular model has many environmental, climate, social and economic benefits.

The circular economy is strongly supported by the European Commission and other EU institutions, as well as by a growing number of cities and countries across the European Union. It also attracts increasing attention from the business community and public and private investors since the circular economy goes beyond resource efficiency and recycling. It provides the framework to develop new business models aimed at increasing the value, use and life of materials, products and assets and designing out waste from production and consumption.¹

Recycling wastes from Paper & Pulp industry (PPI) into new construction products and applications is the main PAPERCHAIN challenge. The EU market introduction of such materials, by the other hand, faces several barriers: material quality achievement, lack of specific standards for most waste uses, EU Member States (MS) different environmental and technical regulatory frameworks, natural and standard raw materials competitiveness, lack of circular economy model implementation investment and tools, lack of social awareness, etc. Altogether, in addition to companies limited financial and technical capacities currently prevent this paradigm shift from happening.

¹ The EIB Circular Economy Guide Supporting the circular transition; European Investment Bank EIB (2020).

Construction materials are regulated under the Regulation (EU) No 305/2011, which establishes the harmonised conditions for their marketing. In this framework, recycled materials have also to get a technical certification for their commercialisation as construction products. In those cases where the target is not under the scope of any harmonized standard, the certification starts through the procurement of a European Assessment Document (EAD) according to the Regulation 305/2011 that will set the basis for a European Technical Approval (ETA) to finally get the CE Marking. Construction sector, indeed, is one of the most conservative Sector against stablishing new materials and application of new standards, its development not being favoured by a burden on multiple regulations across EU and resulting in largely different exploitable frameworks.

In this report, the lessons learnt in each demonstration activities are shown. An analysis of the key factors for the Circular Economy Model implementation done in previous tasks are showed in a very summarized way for an easy fact-sheet style, for a fast and early evaluation. Key factors such as type of waste, regulatory framework, technological and non-technological barriers/enablers, process optimization, equipment needs, exploitation and workability window, social acceptability, replicability potential, etc. are considered. By this approach, each PAPERCHAIN Circular Economy Model (CEM) benefits and replicability potential can be easily understood by the public. Negative aspects as technological gaps, market weakness, regulatory constraints, etc. of each CEM are also outlined to prevent and overcome issues on the potential replication of each interested PAPERCHAIN solution across the EU.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

CC: Circular Case

CEM: Circular Economy Model

DPS: Deinking Paper Sludge

DPA: Deinking Paper Ash

EAD: Environmental Assessment Document

EtCl: Ethyl Chloride

GLD: Green Liquor Dregs

HRB: Hydraulic Road Binder

MS Member States of EU

PPI: Pulp and Paper Industry

PSA: Paper Sludge Ash

QA/QC: Quality Assurance / Quality Control.

SRM: Secondary Raw Materials

WPFA: Waste-Paper Fly Ash

1. Introduction

1.1 Objectives

The objective of this Task 7.3 was to elaborate simplified Management Guidelines doc. (D7.3 "Guidelines for the implementation of the Circular Economy models") for the **5 Circular Economy Models developed in the PAPERCHAIN project**. The guidelines are based on the outcomes obtained from the study of the PAPERCHAIN cases demonstrations (WP4), (WP5), and from the analysis on the potentiality for products certification for market (WP7), and exploitation and replicability potential (WP8) of such CEM. The guidelines aim to facilitate PAPERCHAIN CEM and to be a valuable tool to understand its potential replicability in other scenarios than those developed in PAPERCHAIN and prevent and overcome issues on the potential replication of each interested PAPERCHAIN solution across EU.

The present document includes the compilation of key factors and the lessons learnt for each specific CC. Key recommendations for the establishment of the circular economy cases are provided, considering the experience of the involved stakeholders. The guidelines have been developed with a special focus on allowing the potential future replication of these circular economy models across EU in similar scenarios. Aspects such as regulation, standards, certification, and regional aspects, already studied in the project have been considered for the elaboration of the guidelines. The scope of the guidelines, in any case, is limited to the output obtained in previous tasks of the project, and therefore cannot held with all the potential valorisation scenarios across EU, not analysing deeply all the factors that may affect to the CEM, as those are sufficiently explained in other public documents. Moreover, it pretends to serve as a starting reference for PAPERCHAIN CEM replication.

Guidelines for replication are reported by through each the key points of each Case Study (waste quantity, application performance, actors involved, applicable best process, exploitation window, environmental benefits, etc.), including the lessons learnt in each demonstration activity. The guidelines seek to assist new stakeholders in the implementation and replication of PAPERCHAIN solutions throughout the EU. Task 7.3 involved:

- a) the thorough analysis of most of the project documentation,
- b) the consultation to stakeholders on the gathered experience,
- c) the elaboration of a Guidelines document including a summarized Case by Case "fact sheet" short style document that synthetizes each circular model and key

points, so as to be employed for future dissemination activities and foster the replication of the PAPERCHAIN circular models.

The present document tries to provide simplified Management Guidelines for the Circular Economy Models developed in PAPERCHAIN. The Guidelines are based on the outcomes obtained from the PAPERCHAIN demonstrations cases (WP4), (WP5), the experiences and lessons learnt gained during the project in each pilot, and from the analysis on the products certification (WP7), potential exploitation (WP8) and social awareness, in order to disseminate (WP9) and **facilitate the replication of these models across the EU.**

1.2 Circular Cases description

The following **5 Circular Cases** have been addressed:

Gathering ALL relevant inputs through PAPERCHAIN PROJECT:

5 CIRCULAR MODEL GUIDELINES DOCs

FIGURE 1 – PAPERCHAIN 5 CIRCULAR ECONOMY MODELS.

- **Portuguese Circular Case (CC1):** *Modifying wastes from the Kraft process to produce precast concrete and asphalt pavements with less natural resources for the Road Construction Sector (Figure 2). The Navigator Company (NVG) operates several pulp and paper plants in Portugal, generating annually 32kt of Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs) and Grits as well as 26kt of lime mud wastes, currently, sent to landfills. With the incorporation of such wastes in several construction materials, replacing aggregates or fillers, which can produce a similar performance, relevant environmental and economic benefits are obtained due to the reduction of landfill disposal as well as savings in natural raw materials. . Moreover, the centre region of Portugal has a strong manufacturing sector for construction products, creating a good potential for industrial symbiosis. This demo can be a good example to show and replicate for other sectors the added value of valorisation of wastes as alternative raw materials. Challenges such as material humidity and salts content were overcome in the demonstration pilot activities.*

Two demonstration pilots were carried out:

- 1a) Lime Mud replacing natural limestone fillers in precast concrete elements.*
- 1b) Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs), and slaker grits as secondary raw materials for production of bituminous mixtures for asphalts.*

FIGURE 2 – PAPERCHAIN 5 CC1. CONCRETE AND ASPHALTS ELABORATION IN PORTUGAL.

- **Spanish circular case (CC2):** Wastepaper Sludge Fly Ash (WPSFA) based alternative binder has been employed for replacement of cement or quicklime in soil stabilization works in

road projects (Figure 3). SAICA paper recycling operator (Zaragoza region, Spain), generates 40kt/y fly ash due to its valorisation process. WPFA is known for its hydraulic hardening potential, as fly ash use is ruled by the *EN 13282-2:2015. Hydraulic road binders – part 2: Normal hardening hydraulic road binders*. In this case, successful use, and performance of WPFA substituting partially the cement has been demonstrated in 3 pilots focused on different stabilized soils-based road construction in Spain, carried out by ACCIONA Construcción. For this case, a Technical Conformity (TC) document (D7.2) elaboration has been chosen as a first step to introduce the material in the market in absence of specific Spanish standard for such material. Challenges: WPFA compositional variability regarding to some compounds contain and leaching (heavy metals and chlorides), exploitation issues regarding to environmental risk assessment, workability (dust spreading by wind and hydrogen gas formation) and exploitable window restriction about distances from producer to the application site as a low density material, and standard material pricing and availability.

FIGURE 3 – PAPERCHAIN CC2. ROAD HYDRAULIC BINDERS ELABORATION IN SPAIN.

- **Slovenian circular case (CC3):** The innovative solution is based on a composite material called MUDIPEL®, used as a backfill material behind retaining wall structures for gabions in railway infrastructures (Figure 4). The new composite was made from deinking paper ash (DPA) and deinking paper sludge (DPS) mix produced by VIPAP (Slovenia). A Pilot consisting in gabions for retaining walls against landslides in railway line in the southern part of Slovenia was successfully performed (Dušan Holešek). As this new material is not included in any European standard, the certification had to start through the European Assessment Document (EAD) procedure (ZAG). Challenges such as material mechanical and environmental performance, correct dosage and humidity control of the installation were overcome.

FIGURE 4 – PAPERCHAIN CC3. RETAINING WALLS CONSTRUCTION IN SLOVENIA.

- **Swedish chemical Circular Case (CC4):** The objective of this Circular Case has been the production of high-quality ethyl chloride based on the transformation of the cellulose originated from the pulp mills fibre sludge waste processing (Figure 5). At the end of the cycle, ethyl chloride serves for the Bermocoll® production, a product used in construction as a coating. Through this Circular Case 4 a pilot was carried out in Sweden, replacing fossil- based materials with renewable raw materials and elaborating new sustainable products. Quality requirements for new products must comply with chemical quality and REACH regulation. Challenges such as the new process scalability, safety-human and environmental, and economic feasibility have been the main challenges. This model was based on an interoperation between partners for a successful circular approach, where communication is a clue factor.

FIGURE 5 – PAPERCHAIN CC4. CHEMICALS PRODUCTION IN SWEDEN, OVERALL PROCESS.

-Swedish mining Circular Case (CC5): mining waste covering impermeable layer construction employing Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs) PPI wastes was the main objective of this CC5 (Figure 6). The mining sector is regulated by general national laws, but each new mining operation must be approved under specific environmental approvals regarding emissions and pollutants release to surface and groundwater. Due to this specificity, no certification is available for the sector. Therefore, in this specific case, the market exploitation is constrained to the mining company and its exploitable sites storing a same waste. By this CC5 a pilot was performed in north Sweden, where a stable sealing layer based on GLDs and till (local glacier soils), was produced. Such layer reached proper properties, reducing the hydraulic conductivity, avoiding waste leaching to soils and surficial and groundwaters. The main challenges were related to obtain suitable GLD and till qualities, to apply the correct dosage (stablish or application window), achieve GLD-homogeneous qualities, mixing and packing GLD and till dosages with different qualities and to select the right equipment to handle the mixtures.

FIGURE 6 – PAPERCHAIN CC5. MINING WASTE COVERING LAYER CONSTRUCTION, SWEDEN.

1.2 Circular Economy Models implementation and replication key factors

The implementation and replication of a new Circular Model requires a deep analysis of the main factors that may affect to a correct development. Knowing and understanding the lessons learnt from similar cases studies and pilots and experimental exercises is crucial to avoid the same mistakes and erroneous perspectives.

A successful implementation/replication of CEMs depend on many factors such as:

- ✚ **Waste classification.** Despite the common general EU rules for the classification of waste that allow its use, each MS has its own declassification procedures.

Depending on the EM, the Region and even the municipality, the waste can be classified in different ways (EoW, by-product, etc.). Its direct use and / or transformation as a new secondary raw material makes the waste sorting processes tedious and time consuming due to requirements and administrative burdens, and even expensive in some MS. A successful CEM implementation/replicability requires a favourable and clear and easy waste classification process. The analysis of this aspect should be taken in account before trying to implement a new CEM. The use of certain secondary raw material can be very feasible or not allowed depending on the geographical location.

- 📌 **Technical and quality requirements.** Even if a waste is declassified as waste, and theoretically its use is approved for certain construction applications, frequently, the existing operating technical rules and guidelines, especially those concerning cements, concretes, etc. are very conservative, not specifying the use of the SRM of interest. Demonstration activities, such those developed in PAPERCHAIN, help to change the established regulations, but it may take a long time for advisory boards and administrations before doing any change on them due to the traditional conservative position and, frequently, an opposition of some operators with standard materials can be relevant also. Technical regulations may not close the door for the use of certain secondary raw materials, but does not promote their use neither, as regulatory documents do not strictly mention certain SRMs use in determined applications, and therefore, preventing a real and widespread valorisation. A previous deep analysis of existing favourable EU level, but also, MS, regional, and local technical regulation is necessary prior planning any new CEM.
- 📌 **Facilities and Equipment.** The use of standard ("business as usual") equipment is sought when facing a new CEM. Current equipment suitability facilitates greatly the implementation of new models. Needs for specific machinery designs suppose increased investment, homologation procedures, etc. Therefore, using standard equipment for SRMs valorisation, when possible, supposes a great advantage that must be taken in account. **Skilled personnel.** Planning and driving a whole CEM requires, from a holistic knowledge, the ability to visualize the key factors of its implementation, technical, regulatory, environmental and carbon footprint evaluation, exploitation, etc. The paradigm change precises moving from linear approaches to circular ones, and therefore, to move away from limited company level view, to CEM whole value chain level view. Therefore, understanding also the involved stakeholders' challenges and the framework (legal, market, etc.) of a successful CEM implementation. The lack of experienced and specialized personnel can be a barrier for a successful implementation and replication of any CEM. Communication plays a relevant role in this task.

✚ **SRM supply and use.** SRM availability is not always granted, both regarding to quality and quantities. Regular and homogeneous waste supply is the best base to guarantee a long term and stable CEM. Its achievement has effect on lower logistic costs, stable price framework and increased model efficiency. On the other hand, a stable SRM demand is the other base for long term CEM. Discontinuous SRM demands are typical of certain sectors, such as road construction sector, with big material demand peaks during the construction works, combined frequently with long time-spaced no demand periods. This last fact does complicate SRM logistics -higher storage needs-, add uncertainty to the CEM, etc. and finally can be a major factor for discarding the implementation of any solid CEM. In contrast, already well established business based on standard raw materials have the advantage of a well-known and guaranteed material supply framework, usually with large variety of providers, and therefore, a less risky business.

✚ **Communication.** As in any commercial relationship, a proper communication between stakeholders is crucial for a successful business. In the case of CEMs, even more, since the agents involved in the value chain depend even more from each other value chain agent to get a successful achievement. Key aspects such as continuous and homogeneous quality SRM providing, involves strict quality control and material availability for end-user. In addition, CEM should offer technical and environmental guarantees also for authorities and public, and then opacity in the communication of some information in the context of the activities linked to a CEM is not desirable. Therefore, implementation of a CEM requires a) well established communication between involved stakeholders to share any relevant SRM performance change due to industrial process and waste transformation variation that may involve waste quality modification, b) continuous monitoring on the exploitation feasibility according to changes reported in a), and c) new regulatory, changes in the market and stakeholders ambitions. A proper communication plan is necessary for a solid CEM implementation.

✚ **Policies.** Up to date, the implementation of new CEMs depend greatly from administration policies (D8.4). The design and intensity of these policies can be very different across EU MS, Regions and even Councils. This, in fact, gives a very uneven picture across EU, with MS with more developed regulatory and suitable policies, which in fact are a big clue for promoting any CEM. A more developed policy, usually means an advanced regulatory and guidance framework, a more

stable context, a major investment, a major number of piloting and demonstration activities, bigger amount of skilled personnel capable to drive and evaluate CEM, dedicated companies and facilities, major social awareness, etc.

✚ **Exploitation window.** Most CEMs show a quite narrow exploitation windows, since working with wastes commonly faces extra efforts on: selection and treatment processes, occasionally also new equipment or usual equipment adaptation, an increased monitoring cost, typically bigger costs on transport and storage, plus previous investments on research, piloting and product certification(s), need to disseminate and create of awareness among public and private companies, etc. In addition, CEM must usually compete with other linear models in clear disadvantage (lack of green public purchase policies, etc.). Finally, the -still- usual distrust from the construction sector to new constructions developments based on SRMs, and the regulatory restrictions (maximum natural feedstock substitution rates, lack of clear specification for certain wastes uses, etc.), does not favour the adoption and/or replication of new CEMs. Therefore, constrains in the exploitation window, such as type of intended product and application, quantity of potential SRM valorisation, achievable market price, etc. must be well identified for an intended geographical scenario prior any CEM replication.

✚ **LCA and CO₂ footprint.** The adoption of new CEM paradigms is linked to the efficient use of resources as recycled wastes, but also, the carbon footprint minimization as a key point and advantage of circular models against linear ones. Nevertheless, not all the CEM are suitable for this purpose since it can occur that a new CEM implementation may occasion a major CO₂ footprint unless a correct evaluation is done. For example, the transport of wastes from their production site to its application area is probably the major matter of concern at this moment regarding CO₂ footprint. Competitiveness of a CEM can be limited to a certain exploitation distance radius. SRM characteristics, such as wastes with lower densities, as WPFA for example, requires from major number of transportation events for a same material quantity than other standard materials, meaning an increased cost and CO₂ footprint. Moreover, new applications durability must be thoroughly assessed to avoid implementation of CEMs of a poor LCA balance. This is critical for the cases of large infrastructures construction (roads, railways, etc.), where large investments require from long-term use working conditions. The new CEM should guarantee reasonable long-term performance, which may be questioned by the sector due to the lack of sufficient long-term, small-scale pilot experiences. A poor long-term performance of the new development would produce a major cost and the need of major maintenance works (infrastructures

and constructive applications), increasing at the same time the overall CO₂ footprint.

For all the selected facts presented, it can be deduced that the implementation of a CEM and its replication in the different Ms, regions and councils of the EU, requires a good knowledge of the CEM value chain and the involved key factors., In addition, good knowledge of the specific scenario (geographic location, specific type of SRM, origin and transport footprint, etc.) for which the CEM may or may not work. The study of replication of a certain CEM requires therefore a deep holistic of multiple variable analysis. A single key factor can ruin the implementation of a CEM if not considered previously. In addition, each exploitation site has its own characteristics related to market, regulation and competitiveness of standard materials. Authorities determination favouring CEMs / punishing circular linear models, etc. is another fact to study also.

This document pretends to be a simplified and easy understanding tool as guideline document that can help on the implementation and replication of the Circular Models developed in PAPERCHAIN. For such purpose, a PAPERCHAIN Case by Case analysis is summarized showing the key points and each Case fact sheet elaboration is attached. The need to summarize the circular case and lesson learnt in a brief format has been considered the best way to understand the potential of case implementation and replication in different context by the interested public, stakeholder, etc. in a fast review.. The scope of this document is limited regarding to detailed technical aspects, since each Circular Case is thorough fully explained in other public deliverables already mentioned.

2. Procedure for Guidelines development

The activities for the development of the Guidelines for implementation and replication of the Circular Economy Models are divided into the next steps:

2.1 Review of the existing information

A successful Circular Economy Model implementation requires from a deep survey and analysis of a holistic approach type collected data (Figure 7):

FIGURE 7 – PAPERCHAIN CEM IMPLEMENTATION HOLISTIC ANALYSIS.

Experience shows that any of the determining factors, even without prioritizing, can ruin and impede the implementation of a CEM. For example, restrictive regulation in certain countries and regions regarding the classification and use of waste, relatively low-priced standard materials with high competitiveness and availability, low taxes on waste dumping, but also, technical factors such as salts and the humidity of the waste that must be adapted and / or acquire new equipment, etc. they can make a CEM uncompetitive against standard linear economy models. All the factors that govern a CEM must be aligned with stakeholders and public interests, to make it possible and sustainable over time. For that reason, a CEM implementation requires from a continuous thorough evaluation, from its design at early stages, during the piloting and experimental application, and for its real application. Working with a stable (economic, regulatory, market, carbon footprint taxes, etc.), framework is desirable for such implementation

since, the investment on any technology must be justified easier through time. Therefore, any small fact beforehand can be a definite barrier in some regional, national or EU context, and a big attention must be played to it before launching the replication of any CEM.

This 2.1 aimed to perform a deep review generated through the project, from waste quality and its variability, waste availability, waste transformation and handling issues, workability, regulation in different countries, exploitation window, life-cycle assessment, and carbon footprint, etc. It consisted in mainly in the review of most of the deliverables launched in PAPERCHAIN, and several consultancies meetings held with the stakeholders involved in the research, so gained experience was shared and most interesting lessons learnt extracted from each Pilot Case.

From the consulted Project Documents a major focus was placed on the following deliverables with special remark to the following public Deliverables:

- Implementation of Circular Cases 1 to 5 (D5.1, D5.2, D5.3, D5.4, D5.5).
- Performance analysis of each Circular Case 1 to 5 (D5.6, D5.7, D5.8, D5.9, D5.10)
- D4.3 Recycling analysis of the end-of-life of developed products.
- D2.4 Technological and non-technological barriers and constraints

Also, certification procedures developed for each case in this WP7, when applied, were followed closely, looking to the main key parameters, and Exploitation and replication analysis from WP7 and WP8, and WP6 related to Life Cycle and sustainability assessment.

2.2 Key factors and lessons learnt identification.

Based on the information review mentioned in 2.1, several key factors are shown for each case study. Each Key factor means a regulatory critical aspect, technological or non-technological barrier, equipment gap, process characteristic, waste quality requirement, material workability, etc. that constitute by itself a relevant factor that may impede / facilitate the implementation and replication of each Paperchain Circular Model. Such key factors were already defined by the existing deliverables elaborated in PAPERCHAIN and contrasted by consultancies to the partners and stakeholders involved in the pilots. Most relevant lessons learnt are linked to the correspondent key factors.

- Waste
- Regulatory framework
- Proceedings
- Barriers
- Enablers
- LCA/CO2 footprint

- Exploitation
- Replicability potential

2.3 Circular Models Guideline Fact Sheets

The aim of this task was to elaborate a brief fact sheets type document gathering the essence of each Circular Case, from model explanation, barriers, etc. stakeholders involved, lessons learnt and its reproducibility potential (Figure 8). Fact Sheets are publicavailable in the project website (<https://www.paperchain.eu/>) and Zenodo.

Gathering ALL relevant inputs through PAPERCHAIN PROJECT:

OUTPUT: 5 CIRCULAR MODEL GUIDELINES DOC

- ❖ EXPLAINING the MODEL
- ❖ TARGETED WASTE AND APPLICATIONS
- ❖ MAIN ACTORS
- ❖ BEST IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURES
- ❖ BARRIERS AND ENABLERS
- ❖ REPRODUCIBILITY POTENTIAL IN EU
- ❖ EXPLOITATION WINDOW
- ❖ OTHERS (links of interest, contacts, etc.)

Visual and easy understanding DOC

FIGURE 8 – PAPERCHAIN GUIDELINES FACT SHEET CONCEPT.

The facts sheet style will help sharing the relevant information for each CEM on any dissemination activity such as poster, leaflets, etc. and as starting point for discussion in any

meeting between stakeholders, authorities, public, academics, etc. around the opportunity for implementation and replication of the developed PAPERCHAIN Circular Models. With the support of these circular project's guidelines, best practices, technologies, and lessons learnt.

This fact sheet should be considered as a life document, which can be updated as long new scenario technologies, finding and framework (regulatory, economic, etc.) evolution. Therefore, it can be a quick evaluation tool for CEM implementation opportunity and to understand the challenges faced by each case.

Facts sheet consist on a 3-4 pages document summarizing the PAPERCHAIN 5 CEMs where following items are shown by pages:

Page 1. Shows a short CC explanation and the Case Circular Diagram about pilot demonstration, including waste-process-application.

Page 2. CC pictures: a) waste, b) process, c) end-product.

Pages 3-4. Circular Case stakeholders and Pilot site location identification, waste type, the products and end applications description. Key factors and lessons learnt. Summary of general guidelines.

3. Paperchain Circular Model Guidelines

In PAPERCHAIN, the following waste streams and applications have been considered:

TABLE 1 SUMMARY OF PPI WASTE STREAMS AND APPLICATIONS IN PAPERCHAIN.

<i>Waste stream</i>	<i>Valorization Scenario</i>	<i>Application</i>	<i>Circular Case</i>
Lime ash	Construction manufacturing	Filler aggregate in pre-cast Concrete	1a
Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs) and Slaker Grits (Grits)	Construction manufacturing	Fillers and fine aggregates in asphalt pavements.	1b
Waste Paper Fly Ash (WPFA)	Transport Infrastructures Road Sector	Hydraulic Road Binder applications	2
Deinking Paper Ash (DPA) and Deinking Paper Sludge (DPS)	Transport Infrastructures Railway Sector	Slope stabilization with Gabion wall and back-fill construction material	3
Fibre Sludge	Chemical industry	Ethyl Chloride production as raw material for Bermocoll	4
Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs)	Mining Industry	Mine waste sealing layer for mine reclamation.	5

In this chapter, a brief review (facts sheet) of each Case is carried out focusing on the key factors and lessons learnt as mentioned previously. The following Cases can be checked with more detail in already available public documents (<https://www.paperchain.eu/publications/>).

3.1 Circular Model Guidelines CC1 Construction manufacturing: pre-cast and asphalt pavements.

3. CC1a – Lime ash Concrete Pre-casts.

Circular Case 1a Keywords

concrete	Lime mud	Lime ash	Pre-cast	porticos
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Pre-cast concrete is produced at industrial scale pilot demonstration (Figures 9², 10, 11 and 12) in SPRAL (concrete products manufacturing Portuguese SME), employing, as a filler, the lime ash generated by the NAVIGATOR COMPANY NAV (Pulp and Paper Company), located in Portugal. The new pre-cast concrete performance was compared with the specifications and standard pre-cast concretes. UNIVERSITY OF AVEIRO (UAVR) collaborated with SPRAL and NAV in this Circular Case, for technical support.

FIGURE 9 – CC1 (PORTUGAL). CONSTRUCTION OF PRE-CAST CONCRETES AND ASPHALTS.

² Notice that the circular diagram includes both Case 1a and 1b circular cases.

FIGURE 10 – WASTE. LIME-ASH DERIVED FROM THE INCINERATION OF PAPER LIME-MUD.

FIGURE 11 – PROCESS: CONCRETE REINFORCED PRE-CASTING BASED ON PAPER LIME-ASH.

FIGURE 12 – APPLICATION. CONCRETE PRE-CAST RE-ENFORCED BEAMS IN AND COLUMNS IN PORTICOS.

TABLE 2 PAPERCHAIN CIRCULAR CASE 1A MAIN ITEMS

<i>item</i>	<i>Description</i>
PAPERCHAIN STAKEHOLDERS	NAVIGATOR (waste producer), SPRAL (constructor), UAV (scientific partner)
LOCATION	Ilhavo (Portugal)
WASTE	Lime ash (waste paper result of energetic valorization of PPI lime mud)
PRODUCT	Pre-cast Concrete
APPLICATION	Columns and Beams for construction of porticos.

TABLE 3 CC1A LIME ASH CONCRETE PRE-CASTS. KEY FACTORS AND LESSONS LEARNT.

<i>Key Factor</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Lesson learnt</i>
Waste (Lime Ash)	<p>Composed mainly by calcium carbonate (CaCO_3);</p> <p>Code 03 03 09 in the European List of wastes (2014), classified as non-hazardous waste (decision 2014/955).</p>	<p>Needs no pre-treatment after lime-mud incineration.</p> <p>Relatively free of contaminants</p> <p>Very suitable material as filler</p>
Regulatory framework	<p>UNE-12620, Aggregates for concrete.</p> <p>EN 13225:2013 Precast concrete products (91.100.30 Concrete and concrete products) standard.</p>	<p>No specific regulation for the use of lime ash in pre-cast elements.</p> <p>License obtaining for waste valorization, even at pilot level constitutes nowadays a main barrier for circular cases implementation at Portugal.</p>
Proceedings	<p>"Business as usual" for fillers employed on pre-cast concretes elaboration.</p>	<p>Easily introduced in concrete mixture.</p> <p>Good workability. Similar to natural filler production rate and</p>

		performance of columns and beams. 100% of natural/standard filler replacement achievable.
Barriers	Lack of specific regulation for lime-ash in pre-cast concretes is a major handicap for lime ash valorization.	Lime ash still considered as “waste”. CE marking (CEN route) foreseen as best route for this application.
Enablers	Present Process equipment and facilities employed in pre-cast elaboration with standard fillers are suitable with novel filler.	No substantial process modification. Relatively free of pollutants.
LCA/CO2 footprint	The features and characteristics of the targeted construction products were not hindered or modified by the introduction of these wastes after long term monitoring.	Proven technical and environmental performance and expected long-term performance, similar to those materials with natural fillers. No environmental threat. Lower CO ₂ footprint and increased circularity vs. standard .
Exploitation	The pre-cast elaboration requires from a dry filler (<1%) providing, guaranteed by the incineration process of the lime mud to obtain lime ash stored in dry environment. Market introduction of the lime ash should be highly possible.	Not need to modify the pre-cast elaboration method, and then, no extra investment costs are needed. Competitive CEM if regular (dry) waste supply is provided. Regulatory support and incentives (taxes, green purchases, etc.) can be very variable among Ms. Regulatory in some countries can be a definite barrier for lime ash exploitation.
Replicability potential	Concrete (limestone) fillers that are currently on the market, typically have a competitive cost and well-established extraction industries.	Key factors affecting the market potential such as technical feasibility of use and competitive cost could be successfully addressed by the PAPERCHAIN approach in most of the EU Ms.

CC1a: Concrete pre-cast based on lime ash short Guidelines:

✚ Circular Economy Models using lime ash derived from the energetic valorisation of PPI lime mud waste use in pre-cast concretes as developed in PAPERCHAIN approach (CC1a), are basically limited by its classification as “waste”, and lack of specific legal framework for lime ash use in pre-cast concretes production. Technical and environmental performance and workability according to usual pre-cast elaboration procedures have been proven to be successful, not increasing the process costs. Replicability potential of this CEM is considered of high across EU Ms.

3.1.1. CC1b – GLDs and Grits containing Asphalt pavements.

Circular Case 1b Keywords

Asphalt	Pavement	Grits	GLDs	mixtures
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This Circular Case is focused on the use of treated Grits Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs) as fillers and aggregates on the elaboration of a bituminous mixture of type AC 14 on a road surface layer in an industrial site, substituting standard raw materials. This surface layer road was divided into four sections; 1) a standard bituminous mixture section, 2) a section where the fine aggregates were partially replaced by grits, 3) a section where the fine aggregates were partially replaced by GLD and 4) a section where the fine aggregates were partially replaced by grits and GLDs.

THE NAVIGATOR COMPANY (PPI) produced GLDs and grits wastes were managed by DILUMEX carrying out the material transportation and a needed waste pre-treatment for the elaboration of the asphalt mixture in a mixing facility of MEGAVIA (Constructor). Wastes pre-treatment consists of drying and sieving (particles smaller than 10mm). UNIVERSITY OF AVEIRO (UAVR) collaborated with DILUMEX and NAVIGATOR in this Circular Case, for technical support.

Figure 9 shows the CC1b Circular Case in Portugal. The following Figures 13 to 15 show the industrial scale pilot demonstration.

FIGURE 13 –WASTE: (LEFT) GREEN LIQUOR DREGS (GLDs); (RIGHT) SLAKER GRITS. NAVIGATOR.

FIGURE 14 – PROCESS: A) GLDs AND GRITS DRYING UP, B) ROAD CONSTRUCTION AFTER MIXING.

FIGURE 15 – APPLICATION: ASPHALT PAVEMENTS FOR INDUSTRIAL USE.

TABLE 4 PAPERCHAIN CIRCULAR CASE CC1B MAIN ITEMS

<i>item</i>	<i>Description</i>
PAPERCHAIN STAKEHOLDERS	NAVIGATOR (waste producer), DILUMEX (waste manager), MEGAVIA (Constructor), UAV (scientific partner)
LOCATION	Celulose Bombeiros road, Cacia (Portugal).
WASTE	Slaker Grits (Grits), Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs)
PRODUCT	Asphalt hot mixtures
APPLICATION	Asphalt road pavement

TABLE 5 CC1B ASPHALT PAVEMENT WITH GRITS AND GLDs. KEY FACTORS AND LESSONS LEARNT

<i>Key Factor</i>	<i>Description/fact</i>	<i>Lesson learnt</i>
Wastes (Grits , GLDs)	<p><u>Grits</u>: non-hazardous waste. Ejects from the lime kiln and limestone fragments precipitated during causticizing reactions. Contain sodium and aluminum salts and are strongly alkaline. Low content of elements of concern and low leachability of metals, chloride, fluoride and sulphate. Low contains of Dissolved Organic Carbon (DOC) and Total Dissolved Solids (TDS).</p> <p><u>GLDs</u>: non-hazardous waste. High calcite content, alkaline -high buffering capacity. Low trace elements concentration, not relevant hazardous compounds leaching concerns but some salts. Low hydraulic conductivity.</p>	<p>PPI’s causticizing non-hazardous residuals that are currently mainly disposed to landfill (95% of disposal rate).</p> <p>GLDs and Grits are environmentally acceptable for the application, but GLDs content of salts can be excessive. Need salts washing.</p> <p>High humidity (16-40%) on both wastes. Need for drying up before using.</p>

<p>Regulatory framework</p>	<p>EN-13043: aggregates for bituminous mixtures and surface treatments for roads, airfields and other trafficked areas (2002).</p> <p>EN 13108-1: "Bituminous mixtures – Material specifications – Part 1: Asphalt concrete"</p>	<p>Lack of specific and harmonized EU regulation for the use of Grits / GLDs in construction works.</p> <p>These materials are non-hazardous wastes instead by-products or EoW. This fact suppose an important barrier for an easy adoption</p>
<p>Proceedings</p>	<p>The process of GLDs and Grits valorizing may imply a pre-treatment based on drying and sieving. For some GLDs and Grits currents salts removal will be probably necessary also.</p>	<p>The PAPERCHAIN experience only required drying and sieving process.</p> <p>"Extra" process drying can be done by natural energy employing facilities (greenhouse) and machinery for materials occasional removal.</p> <p>New skills and proceedings on Grits/GLDs waste efficient treatment is required to be included in the CEM value chain.</p>
<p>Barriers</p>	<p>Drying, sieving (and washing) process, plus enviromnetal controls can add an important cost to the valorization process.</p> <p>Lack of harmonized and specific regulation of using Grits/GLDs prevent their use.</p> <p>% of substitution of natural filler and aggregates by GLDs is limited.</p>	<p>Aggregates availability and treatment and storage logistics are more complex than standard raw materials (fillers and aggregates) handling.</p> <p>"Low cost" alternatives must be employed for waste treatment.</p>
<p>Enablers</p>	<p>After Grits/GLDs are treated, their use and workability can be similar to standard aggregates.</p>	<p>Standard working equipment for mixtures and road making can be employed after waste treatment. Not needs for a special machinery adaptation for asphalt production.</p>
<p>LCA/CO2 footprint</p>	<p>Throughout 1-year, a visual and performance monitoring was performed. Good mechanical and</p>	<p>The features and characteristics of the targeted construction products were not hindered or modified by</p>

	<p>environmental performance was observed.</p>	<p>the introduction of these wastes after long-term monitoring.</p> <p>Successful incorporation of Grits / GLDs to bituminous road pavements.</p>
<p>Exploitation</p>	<p>GLDs and Grits landfilling costs as a exploitation driver, where nearly all GLDs and Grits are actually landfilled.</p> <p>The current robust and well-established supply chain of raw materials for the sector is one of the main market entree barriers that the PAPERCHAIN product will have to deal with.</p>	<p>Uncertainties about their quality and long-term performance may remain in the sector.</p> <p>Competitive prices are not guaranteed by the new process, as costs from salts removal (for some GLDs), drying and sieving may require a case by case specific detailed evaluation.</p> <p>The main obstacle resides actually in the negotiations with the public administration about the status of waste. The legal use of “waste” material depends on public authorisation that can delay the market uptake of the SRM.</p>
<p>Replicability potential</p>	<p>EU market is huge (close to 280M tonnes produced in 2019) and in an increasing number of countries, reclaimed asphalt and/or demolition waste is reused/recycled to replace virgin aggregates and part of the binder (EAPA, 2019).</p>	<p>Sustainability principles of the Circular Economy Action Plan, as “increasing re-used and recycled content in products, while ensuring their performance and safety” are increasingly adopted by the sector.</p> <p>The adoption of different waste clasification and use regulation strategies across EU is the major constrain for CC1b replication.</p> <p>Apart of waste availability, the use of low carbon footprint and alternative low-cost technologies for GLDs and Grits treatment can vary from MS, and therefore, the economic feasibility and the replication oportunity for this CEM.</p>

CC1b (Asphalts based on Grits and GLDs) Guidelines:

✚ Circular Economy Models using Grits and Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs) as aggregates in asphalt road pavements as developed in PAPERCHAIN approach (CC1b), are basically limited by its classification as “waste”, the lack of specific legal framework promoting their use, and extra cost coming from their treatment based on salts removal, drying and sieving. Technical and environmental performance and workability according to usual bituminous road layer construction procedures have been proven to be successful, not increasing the process costs, and giving a good technical and environmental long-term performance. Replicability potential of this CEM is considered of high potential across EU Ms.

3.2 Circular Model Guidelines CC2 Construction: roads with WPFA based HRB binders.

Circular Case 2 Keywords

Soil Cement	Stabilisation	Leaching	Binder	roads
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Circular Model CC2 is focused on Wastepaper Fly Ash (WPFA) based hydraulic road binder (HRB) production for soil stabilization in road construction sector. ACCIONA (Constructor) and SAICA (PPI waste valoriser located at El Burgo de Ebro, Zaragoza, Spain) that generates the WPFA, have been cooperating in PAPERCHAIN to find an alternative and sustainable solution for the use of fly ash waste other than landfilling. In this CC2 the ash replaces standard binder (cement) typically employed in the stabilization of soils S-EST2, S-EST3 type layers (according to the PG3³) in rural roads, and a soil-cement layer in highway. 3 Pilots have been successfully completed in different locations in Spain: a) unpaved rural road (Ejea de los Caballeros, Zaragoza), b) paved peri urban road (Villamayor de Gállego, Zaragoza); c) A31 highway (La Font de la Figuera, Valencia). UPC (University), and TECNALIA (Research Center) have supported CC2 in product design, and the technical and environmental performance monitoring. Figure 16 shows the CC2 Circular Case in Spain, and Figures 17-19 show the industrial scale pilot demonstration.

FIGURE 16 – CC2 CIRCULAR CASE (SPAIN). CONSTRUCTION OF ROAD LAYERS WITH WPFA.

³ “Pliego de Prescripciones Técnicas Generales para obras de carreteras y puentes (PG-3)”.

FIGURE 17 – WASTE. WPFA DERIVED FROM THE INCINERATION OF RECYCLING PAPER WASTE (SAICA).

FIGURE 18 – PROCESS: (UP) STABILIZING A SOIL WITH WPFA AT EJA AND VILLAMAYOR (ZARAGOZA) PILOTS; (DOWN) SOIL-CEMENT LAYER AT LA FONT DE LA FIGUERA (VALENCIA).

FIGURE 19 – APPLICATION. (LEFT) RURAL (UNPAVED), PERI URBAN (PAVED) AND HIGHWAY (RIGHT)

TABLE 6 PAPERCHAIN CIRCULAR CASE 2 ROADS BASED ON WPFA, MAIN ITEMS

<i>item</i>	<i>Description</i>
PAPERCHAIN STAKEHOLDERS	SAICA (WPFA producer), ACCIONA CONSTRUCCIÓN (Constructor); UPC and TECNALIA (Research partners)
LOCATION	Pilot 1 in Ejea de los Caballeros (Zaragoza, -SPAIN-). Stabilized soil type 2. Pilot 2 in Villamayor de Gállego (Zaragoza, -SPAIN-). Stabilized soil type 1. Pilot 3 in La Font de la Figuera (Valencia, -SPAIN-). Soil-cement layer.
WASTE	Waste Paper Fly Ash (WPFA)
PRODUCT	Alternative binder for replacement of cement or quicklime in soil stabilization works in road projects. Normal hardening hydraulic road binders (nHRB).
APPLICATION	Stabilized soil layers and soil-cements for different type of roads (rural, urban, Highway, paved and unpaved roads).

TABLE 7 CC2 HRB BINDERS BASED ON WPFA. KEY FACTORS AND LESSONS LEARNT

<i>Key Factor</i>	<i>Fact</i>	<i>Lessons learnt</i>
Waste (WPFA)	Waste Paper Fly ash (WPFA): classified as no-hazardous. Chlorides and Aluminium rich waste. Light weight material.	WPFA composition can be very variable depend on recycling plant technology. Chlorides and heavy metals must be specifically monitored to avoid uncorrect technical and environmental performance. Material low density can suppose an increased transportation costs.
Regulatory framework	UNE EN 13282-1:2013 Hydraulic road binders EU Standard permits to employ paper sludge ash (WPA).	Incompatibility or lack of specific regulation about the use of WPFAs in road construction for certain

	<p>Some MS, such as Spanish regulatory framework does not recognize EN 13282. In addition, Binders obtained through mixing of their constituents on site are not covered by this European Standard</p>	<p>countries limits the application possibilities.</p>
<p>Proceedings</p>	<p>WPFA production conditions in plant can be well controlled and be homogeneous to provide a regular quality WPFA. A more difficult condition suppose on-site WPFA-soil mixing.</p> <p>Actual mixing processes can be adapted to work with the WPFAs as binders in soil stabilization.</p>	<p>WPFA can replace cement satisfactorily, while environmental risks can be acceptable if correct proceedings are followed.</p> <p>“Business as usual” processing of WPFAs as binders in hydraulic road binders can be achieved.</p> <p>Dust generation during the construction works must be minimized when on site mixing, to avoid any environmental problem.</p>
<p>Barriers</p>	<p>Lack of specific regulation on WPFAs use as binder.</p> <p>WPFA lower density.</p> <p>WPFA are produced in few plants across EU.</p>	<p>WPFA classification as “waste” generates distrust and prevent its valorization by the sector. Standard alternatives are still cheap.</p> <p>WPFA low density limits its marketable maximum radius due to higher transportation costs respect to other standard binders.</p>
<p>Enablers</p>	<p>WPFA based soil layers mechanical properties, workability, and even environmental performance achieve the required quality.</p>	<p>WPFA technical suitability in binder replacement for road construction.</p>
<p>LCA/CO2 footprint</p>	<p>All pilots have shown a good technical performance after 3 years and no environmental impacts have been identified, showing a similar trend in metal mobility to other conventional stabilisations.</p>	<p>WPFA has demonstrated its ability as hydraulic road binder, complying with all technical requirements established in the Spanish Road Regulations, equiparable to EU construction standards.</p> <p>Use of WPFA binders reduce the carbon footprint and increase</p>

	<p>Quicklime or other standard binders have a greater carbon footprint.</p>	<p>circularity rate. Nevertheless, the CO₂ footprint derived from WPFA transportation must be well analysed prior CEM is planned to avoid higher CO₂ footprint. A maximum transportation ratio, must be defined, depending on the available transportation type.</p>
<p>Exploitation</p>	<p>Customers (Public and Authorities), demand guarantees about the WPFA quality, and more evidences about soil stabilization long-term performance (durability, mechanical strength, etc.). Demand of more evidences.</p> <p>Exploitation is highly limited to a closer maximum feasibility ratio than a standard binder due to its low density – increased transportation costs.</p> <p>No incentives for WPFA valorization in some MS.</p>	<p>Product certification according to EN 13282-2 is not possible in this case, so that, ACCIONA is applying for a Technical Conformity (TC). The process has already been launched with the Notified Body representatives (TECNALIA) Certification of the product quality is mandatory for its introduction in the market as construction material.</p>
<p>Replicability potential</p>	<p>High replication potencial through several WPFA producing plants across EU.</p>	<p>Limited its use to areas close to WPFA producers and considering a lower transportation ratios than standard fillers.</p> <p>Environmental performance: WPFA composition (chlorides, heavy metals) must be monitorized since they can be very variable among WPFA producers. The application scenario can be more or less environmenatly sensible, then , the risk analysis must be specific to case.</p>

CC2 WPFA based hydraulic road binders short Guidelines:

- ✚ Circular Economy Models using waste paper fly ash (WPFA) derived from the energetic valorisation of paper waste use in hydraulic road binders as developed in PAPERCHAIN approach (CC2), are limited by its classification as “waste”, its and lack of specific legal framework promoting WPFA use in hydraulic road binders production. Technical and environmental performance and workability according to usual nHRB binder elaboration procedures have been proven to be successful, with affordable process costs. Replicability potential of this CEM is considered of high potential across EU Ms.

3.3 Circular Model Guidelines CC3: Transport infrastructure sector- railways. MUDIPEL®.

Circular Case 3 Keywords

Back-fill material	Deinking paper ash (DPA)	Deinking paper sludge (DPS)	Gabion	railways
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This Circular Model CC3 is focused on the use of an innovative composite, with the market name MUDIPEL®, originated from PPI wastes as light backfill alternative material in gabions construction at railways landslides restoration in Slovenia. The composite is a mix of 70 % of deinking paper ash (DPA) and 30 % of deinking paper sludge (DPS). After compaction can develop a considerable strength (>1 MPa at 28 curing days) and low permeability, achieving optimal properties for the intended use. VIPAP (PPI industry) collaborates with Dušan Holešek (construction SME) and ZAG (Research institute and notifying body granted the Slovenian Technical Approval (STS), and SZ Infrastructure (Railways infrastructure operator, end User). TECNALIA supported in the environmental performance monitoring design and validation. Figure 20 shows the CC3 Circular Case in Slovenia. Construction of MUDIPEL based construction designs for railways slopes stabilisation. The following Figures 21 to 23 show the industrial scale pilot demonstration.

FIGURE 20 – C3 CIRCULAR CASE (SLOVENIA). LANDSLIDES STABILISATION WITH MUDIPEL.

FIGURE 21 – WASTE. DPA + DPS = MUDIPEL®. BACK-FILL LIGHT MATERIAL.

FIGURE 22 – PROCESS. RETAINING WALL CONSTRUCTION WITH MUDIPEL®.

Before:

After:

FIGURE 23 – APPLICATION. RETAINING WALL WITH MUDIPEL®.

TABLE 8 PAPERCHAIN CIRCULAR CASE 3 LANDSLIDE STABILIZATION, MAIN ITEMS

<i>item</i>	<i>Description</i>
PAPERCHAIN STAKEHOLDERS	VIPAP (DPA/DPS wastes producer PPI) , Dušan Holešek (Construction SME); SZ infrastructure (Railway manager); ZAG (Research institute); TECNALIA (Research Centre).
LOCATION	South Slovenia, between Ljubljana and Novo Mesto.
WASTE	Deinking Paper Ash (DPA) + Deinking Paper Sludge (DPS)
PRODUCT	MUDIPEL®
APPLICATION	Back fill material for slope stabilization for retaining walls (gabions) in near railways.

TABLE 9 CC3 MUDIPEL BASED GABIONS. KEY FACTORS AND LESSONS LEARNT

<i>Key Factor</i>	<i>Fact</i>	<i>Lessons learnt</i>
Waste (DPA+DPS)	<p>Deinking Paper Ash (DPA)</p> <p>Deinking Paper Sludge (DPS)</p> <p>Non-hazardous wastes of similar chemical and mineralogical compositions.</p>	<p>MUDIPEL (70% DPA + 30% DPS) meets all technical requirements from STS (Slovenian Technical Approval).</p> <p>Do not experience critical volumetric changes, is an impermeable material. Technical and environmentally suitable.</p>
Regulatory framework	<p>Lack of specific regulation and EU standards about the use of DPS and PSA in gabion constructions.</p> <p>Sharp environmental constrains in some Ms (such as Slovenia) for use of these wastes.</p>	<p>Lack of specific regulation about DPS and DPA individual use as back-fill material in construction (gabions, retaining walls, etc.), or as a mix, as MUDIPEL®, can be overcome by Slovenian Technical Approval (STS - Slovenian Technical Approval procedure) for Slovenian market, and for EU market through EAD doc.</p>

	<p>STS - Slovenian Technical Approval procedure for MUDIPEL® granted.</p> <p>EAD in preparation</p>	<p>In any case, getting approvals supposes a big resources and time consuming process.</p>
<p>Proceedings</p>	<p>Challenges: procuring regular availability and “homogeneous” quality SRM for MUDIPEL® production.</p> <p>Mixing, homogenization and compaction are critical.</p> <p>The material can be installed in at least 30cm thick layers.</p>	<p>Constrains on optimal workability time after mixing (<4h).</p> <p>Compaction at works site may need more effort than usual materials.</p> <p>MUDIPEL® characteristics enables constructor building less gabions construction per same length.</p> <p>New skills, and new mixing equipment are needed. Continuous control during the production, mixing and installation stages of MUDIPEL is necessary in order to get high quality back-fill material.</p>
<p>Barriers</p>	<p>Lack of specific regulation and EU standards about the use of DPS and PSA in railways gabion constructions.</p> <p>Lack of many experiences on MUDIPEL® based end-product long-term technical and environmental performance. Yet some lack of confidence from the construction sector.</p>	<p>EU specific regulation and standards about the use of DPA and DSA is necessary to boost the use of such materials.</p> <p>Technical and environmental performance very long term (several years of functioning) to be demonstrated and disseminated yet.</p>
<p>Enablers</p>	<p>DPA and DPS waste landfilling not possible in Slovenia, but abroad (Austria). Elevated landfilling costs (80-150€/ton). Main enabler.</p> <p>The use of MUDIPEL improves the stability of the slope, not supposing a negative impact for the environment.</p>	<p>MUDIPEL® offers a good technical and environmental performance according to the period of pilot observation (2 year). Longer period performance to be demonstrated.</p> <p>Potential use in other applications in the construction sector (roads,</p>

	<p>Impermeability confirmed with the monitoring system installed in the retaining wall.</p> <p>MUDIPEL is a light-weight material with really high shear strength parameters.</p>	<p>mining) are promising. This can boost the use of MUDIPEL®.</p>
<p>LCA/CO2 footprint</p>	<p>MUDIPEL® supposes an increase of the circularity index of construction of gabions, as alternative to standard natural raw materials, while a reduction of the CO₂ footprint.</p>	<p>Carbon footprint reduction is limited by its transportation from MUDIPEL production facility to the construction site.</p> <p>Recyclability of constructed material can be granted if correct dismantling is applied.</p>
<p>Exploitation</p>	<p>MUDIPEL® as new light back-fill material.</p> <p>Exploitation will be possible in Slovenia as STS technical approval is granted. For the rest of EU market still not possible. Unique potential location for MUDIPEL® production (VIPAP) at the moment.</p> <p>-High DPA and DPS landfilling constrains and costs are the main factor for pushing for a DPA and DPS valorization.</p> <p>Additional effort on compaction at works and long-term monitoring may increase the overall construction costs.</p>	<p>MUDIPEL® production can be reproduced in other EU similar facilities.</p> <p>Lack of specific regulation and standard about DPA / DPS use as back-fill material impedes a faster market penetration.</p> <p>Each Ms has a very different technical regulation and requirements regarding to railway and slopes stability and environmental requirements that may impede a homogeneous market penetration.</p> <p>Construction is a very conservative sector but novel constructions with lighter materials as MUDIPEL® in roads and mining reclamation are to be explored.</p>
<p>Replicability potential</p>	<p>MUDIPEL® has a big potential as a back-fill material in railway slope stabilization, but also, as alternative light and impermeable material in other construction applications.</p>	<p>CC3 CEM can be reproduced in other EU Ms PPI similar facilities.</p>

CC3 landslide stabilization backfill material with DPA/DPS paper wastes, short Guidelines:

✚ Circular Economy Models using non-hazardous Deinking Paper Ash (DPA) and Deinking Paper Sludge (DPS) wastes derived from the caustic process of PPI industry as back-fill material (MUDIPEL®) is developed in PAPERCHAIN approach (CC3). Despite the lack of specific EU regulation and standards about DPA / DPS use as back-fill material impeding a wide and faster market penetration, MUDIPEL® shows an optimal technical and environmental performance to be confirmed for longer period of monitoring. MUDIPEL® elaboration requires a proper material handling, homogeneous mixing and compaction that suppose acquiring new skills and adapted equipment. Nevertheless, the technical complexity of working with DPA/DPS for MUDIPEL elaboration and posterior construction can be feasible for the sector considering existing industrial equipment. Replicability potential of this CEM has a geographical limited scope for the moment focused to Slovenia (STS granted).

3.4 CC4 Circular Model Guidelines: fiber sludge-based chemicals production.

Circular Case 4 Keywords

Rejected Fibers	ethanol	hydrolysis	reactor	Bermocoll®
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This Circular Model CC4 demonstrates the transformation of an industrial waste from the PPI to a functional chemical used as an additive in paint and for applications within the construction sector. The circular case is demonstrated by a project group consisting of: DOMSJÖ FABRIKER (pulp mill), that produces dissolving pulp for viscose applications, ethanol from fiber reject and improved pulp quality suitable for production of cellulose ethers; SEKAB (chemical company), that produces ethanol derivatives such as acetic aldehyde and ethyl acetate starting from ethanol, and in addition, ethyl chloride production; NOURYON (Former AKZONOVEL facility), a chemical company with a production of a cellulose ether, Bermocoll®, using cellulose and ethyl chloride as raw materials; where RISE PROCESSUM (research institute), coordinates the circular case and support scientifically the project. Figure 24 shows the CC4 Circular Case in Sweden. Production chemicals from PPI fiber sludges. The following Figures 25 to 27 show the industrial scale pilot demonstration.

FIGURE 24 – CC4 CIRCULAR CASE (SWEDEN)–CHEMICALS FROM FIBER SLUDGE.

FIGURE 25 – WASTES: FIBER SLUDGE.

CC4 – Biorefinery in Örnsköldsvik, Sweden

paperChain

FIGURE 26 – WASTES: FIBER SLUDGE.

FIGURE 27 – APPLICATION. CHEMICALS: IMPROVED CELLULOSE, BIOETHANOL DERIVATIVES, ETHYL CHLORIDE, BERMOCOLL®.

TABLE 10 PAPERCHAIN CIRCULAR CASE 4: CHEMICALS; MAIN ITEMS

<i>item</i>	<i>Description</i>
PAPERCHAIN STAKEHOLDERS	ADIYA BIRLA Domsjö Fabriker (DOMJSO); SEKAB; NOURYON (Former AKZONOVEL facility); SP Processum (SP).
LOCATION	Örnsköldsviks, Sweden.
WASTE	Fiber sludge
PRODUCT	Chemicals: improved cellulose, bioethanol derivatives, Ethyl chloride, Bermocoll®.
APPLICATION	Chemical industry: additives for paintings, coverings, etc.

TABLE 11 CC4 FIBER SLUDGE BASED CHEMICALS. KEY FACTORS AND LESSONS LEARNT

<i>Key Factor</i>	<i>Fact</i>	<i>Lessons learnt</i>
Waste (Fiber sludge)	<p>Fiber sludge comprises cellulose and hemicellulose as main constituents. Waste fiber sludge is produced as a side product at most pulp mills and is usually used for internal energy production.</p> <p>Fibers are short and do not qualify to make paper. Usually fiber reject is incinerated for steam production</p> <p>Composition differs between mills.</p>	<p>Two different types of fiber rejects identified as potential raw materials for sugar production: fines and knot reject.</p> <p>Residual sugars obtained from the fiber sludge generated by DOMSJÖ FABRIKER were used for the ethanol production.</p>
Regulatory framework	<p>Constrains focuses on the product required quality-purity achievement and environmental performance, ruled by REACH.</p>	<p>Important changes in the quality/purity levels for the ethyl chloride may affect dramatically the viability of the new production,</p>

	<p>Obtaining all the environmental permits from authorities, and fulfilling all requirements about safety for the implementation at industrial scale can be challenge and time-consuming (2-3 years approx.).</p> <p>Fossil based chemical productions can be affected by future constraining regulations.</p>	<p>and therefore, major efforts are put in the process optimization.</p> <p>Environmental barriers regarding to production wastewater must be considered, where effluents must be properly monitored and managed.</p> <p>New policies and regulatory framework fostering green chemicals and constrain long distance trading of such chemicals can help boost CC4 products.</p>
Proceedings	<p>Providing a regular SRM quality requires an important effort on quality assuring for the full process.</p> <p>REACH and Quality standards must be granted in all the production steps.</p>	<p>A clear and open fibre sludge traceability is relevant. Therefore, the waste quality control is critical, that implies a solid SRM providing networking.</p> <p>Specific technologies/processes must be developed and upscaled the Electrolysis technology, the transformation of Fiber reject to ethanol via enzymatic hydrolysis, the production of new cellulose quality, the production of Ethyl Chloride.</p>
Barriers	<p>Obtaining high purity chemicals in a feasible way is in fact a big challenge.</p>	<p>To develop these processes, resulting in a high purity production supposes a large investment.</p>
Enablers	<p>Fibre sludge landfilling not allowed in some countries.</p> <p>EtCl availability will be very close, supposing an advantage (neighbours), on costs and environmental footprint.</p>	<p>Solid SRM providing networking is necessary to stablish a stable market framework.</p>
LCA/CO2 footprint	<p>The circular model will replace another no bio product (EtCl) imported by train from Germany.</p>	<p>By this CC4 the overall environmental impact and CO₂ footprint is minimized, making this</p>

	<p>Positive environmental impact is foreseen. All the stakeholders are neighbours so no transport of Ethyl chloride will be required, reduction of carbon footprint.</p>	<p>novel product more attractive than standard fossil-based products.</p>
<p>Exploitation</p>	<p>Domsjö Fabriker will have an increase in the ethanol production and a more versatile cellulose product. A 2000 t/year of high quality ethanol is foreseen by upscaling the process.</p> <p>Sekab have the potential to expand their product portfolio with ethyl chloride which will include the construction of a new chemical plant.</p> <p>Nouryon will be able to produce a more sustainable product while also securing the raw material supply of ethyl chloride.</p>	<p>Competitive new product ethyl chloride prices can be obtained but CC4 implementation costs are high.</p> <p>Increased product and sub-products analyses and purification costs may affect negatively to the margin.</p> <p>Process (ACL) requiring salts storage needs mean higher investment costs.</p> <p>Higher environmental monitoring and safety providing costs will reduce profitability.</p> <p>No other large-scale market opportunity for bio EtCl than Nouryon in EU.</p>
<p>Replicability potential</p>	<p>Ethanol is a global commodity that is a part of the transition to a bioeconomy in Europe and all sources of raw material for ethanol production have to be considered. Wood based fibres are a highly interesting substitution of cotton linter due to problems with irrigation and use of pesticides in cotton production. Bermocoll® and other cellulose ethers are produced at several locations worldwide and could replace fossil based products in additional applications with further development.</p>	<p>No other large-scale market opportunity for bio EtCl than Nouryon in EU.</p> <p>This CC4 process is highly specific and dependent on the new target chemicals envisaged for the replication of the circular economy model.</p>

CC4 chemicals production based on rejected fiber sludge, short Guidelines:

- ✦ The Circular Economy Model CC4 focused on producing improved cellulose, ethanol derivatives, ethyl chloride, and Bermocoll® derived from the fiber sludge developed in PAPERCHAIN approach (CC4) represents a greener and alternative to fossil-based way to produce chemicals. Challenges identified are achieving high quality and purity chemicals, reaction process optimization and new skills for a safe and economically feasible production. High investment in industrial scalable production is required nevertheless, but in the other hand, the large-scale market opportunity for bio EtCl production is unique, representing an alternative lower CO₂ footprint process, that reduces transportation footprint and costs, resulting in an increased competitiveness.

3.5 CC5 Circular Model Guidelines: Mine waste sealing layer based on Green Liquor Dregs (GLD)

Circular Case 5 Keywords

Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs)	till	Sealing layer	leachates	mixing
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This Circular Model CC5 demonstrates the transformation of the pulp and paper industry waste Green Liquor Dreg (GLD) to a functional and alternative material for covering mining wastes to reduce raw material consumption in their reclamation projects. The circular case is demonstrated by a project group consisting of BILLERUDKORSNÄS (pulp mill), GLDs producer, RAGNSELLS (waste manager and constructor) that manipulates GLDs and build the demonstrator, BOLIDEN MINERAL (Mining company), providing the demonstration site, and the technical assistance in relation with mining procedures and requirements for soil covers, mining waste provision and handling recommendations, together with SP-PROCESSUM (Research Institute), and LTU (Luleå University) for scientific support. Figure 28 shows the CC5 Circular Case in Sweden, and Figures 29-31 show the industrial scale pilot demonstration.

FIGURE 28 – CC5 CIRCULAR CASE (SWEDEN)– MINING WASTE COVERING LAYER WITH GLDS.

FIGURE 29 – WASTES: GREEN LIQUOR DREGS (GLDs).

FIGURE 30 – PROCESS: MIXING AND LAYER CONSTRUCTION BASED ON GLDs AND TILL (SOIL)

FIGURE 31 – APPLICATION: MINING RESTORATION WITH GLD BASED IMPERMEABLE LAYERS.

TABLE 12 CIRCULAR CASE 5: MINING RESTORATION – SEALING LAYERS; MAIN ITEMS

<i>item</i>	<i>Description</i>
PAPERCHAIN STAKEHOLDERS	BILLERUDKORSNÄS (pulp mill), RAGNSELLS (waste manager and constructor), BOLIDEN MINERAL (Mining company), SP-PROCESSUM (Research Institute), and LTU (University) for scientific support.
LOCATION	BOLIDEN facilities at Näsliden (north of Sweden).
WASTE	Green Liquor Dregs (GLD)
PRODUCT	Impermeable layer based on GLD mixed and compacted with local soils (Till).
APPLICATION	Mining wastes covering sealing (impermeable) layer based on GLD and Tills for mining waste covering in mining reclamation works.

TABLE 13 CC5 GLD BASED SEALING LAYERS. KEY FACTORS AND LESSONS LEARNT

<i>Key Factor</i>	<i>Fact</i>	<i>Lessons learnt</i>
Waste (GLD)	<p>GLDs are non-hazardous waste from the filtration and recirculation of chemicals (green liquor) in the process. GLDs contain sodium and calcium minerals, black carbon and many other elements. low content of leachable metals.</p> <p>Retrieved through filtration, GLDs are fine grained (silt, clay), have a high-water content (wet), and high-water retention capable.</p>	<p>GLDs can contribute by its properties to hinder oxygen transport to mine waste and can replace bentonite.</p> <p>GLDs can be very variable in its nature, humidity % and water absorption capacity.</p> <p>Optimum Quality Control (testing) need to be implemented. Each mill generates different GLDs qualities.</p>
Regulatory framework	<p>Lack of standards for the use of GLDs in construction applications. Untill now GLDs are landfilled.</p> <p>There is no formal regulation on whether the GLDs can be used in</p>	<p>There is no general rule for all mining sites and each mining operation must be approved under specific environmental permitting regarding emissions and pollutants release to</p>

	<p>mine waste remediation in Sweden or not, neither in EU</p>	<p>surface and ground waters. Sealing layers must fulfil specific (local) functional requirements.</p> <p>New standards for their use in construction applications should be developed for a widespread use.</p>
<p>Proceedings</p>	<p>GLD storage and handling require some specific facilities: mixing and application construction under rain conditions are not suitable or not desirable.</p> <p>Workability Window: a good quality control on mixture physical-mechanical properties and humidity is critical and may be a challenge.</p> <p>Organizational and technological changes are required respect a standard material based construction.</p>	<p>Providing a regular GLD and soil quality can be a challenge: regular and homogeneous GLD and Soil can be very changeable, and then, it can affect relevantly to the process effectivity. Frequently, the soil can be more heterogeneous than the waste itself.</p> <p>Optimal till soils for mixing may be scarce, and are provided as a waste originated from excavation works in the building sector (houses, roads, etc.). The application should be enough flexible to adapt to available soil qualities, usually very heterogeneous for several scenarios. Soil quality and origin (avoiding polluted or altered soils), should be check in each case.</p> <p>Mixing process may be complicated for achieving a homogeneous mixing product, and therefore, determining exhaustively a workability window for each case is fundamental. Layer performance achievement can be difficult if raw materials are not well selected and mixed and works are done out of the workability window.</p> <p>Raining periods must be avoided for the construction process.</p> <p>Changes in supplies and adptation in mixing equipment introduce operational changes, then skilled</p>

		workers on new process and long-term monitoring are needed.
Barriers	<p>Total Organic Carbon (TOC) excess may difficult its valorization supposing a potential barrier.</p> <p>Distance of waste producer to mining sites. Economic feasibility, carbon footprint.</p> <p>Soils heterogeneity requires an specific dosage in each application.</p> <p>GLD production at this moment is smaller than mining restoration material needs.</p> <p>Concerns on long-term environmental performance and liabilities.</p>	<p>Detected TOC has more relationship with the black carbon content and on the analytical methodology usually applied.</p> <p>Experience using and monitoring GLDs based layers will probably demand a better sorting and an improvement of the generated pulp residue and the soils, implying new treatment solutions and dedicated personnel for the PPI industry.</p> <p>Long-term Paperchain Pilot monitoring showed a preliminary good performance achieving expected requirements set by the end-user, long-term performance is still to be demonstrated and will need several years of monitoring in order for a definite conclusion to be established.</p>
Enablers	<p>Effect of the leachate (percolating precipitation) on the underlying mine waste and the recipient, monitoring those parameters (metals and anions) according to regional laws.</p>	<p>Environmental performance as the effect of the leachate (percolating precipitation) on the underlying mine waste and the recipient, monitoring parameters (metals and anions) according to regional laws.</p> <p>Technical performance as the mechanical properties of the layer achieving mining operator requirements.</p>
LCA/CO2 footprint	<p>Positive effect, as mining waste reduced by another waste.</p>	<p>CO₂ footprint dependant on waste and soil transportation distance.</p>

<p>Exploitation</p>	<p>Site mine restoration project requirements may require very high-specific solution, increasing the costs.</p> <p>Standard and well known solutions (geotextiles) are competitive and easy to adopt. There may be resistance for changes.</p> <p>Customers and Public may be suspicious of the effectiveness long-term of the protective layers, since they are performed by SRMs. Enough technical long-term evidences would support the solution.</p>	<p>Financial return highly dependent on the distance from source materials to working site more than applying the technologies developed in PAPERCHAIN.</p> <p>Monitoring costs can suppose an important cost for this application unless standardization is developed.</p> <p>Provision of quality GLD and Till soils may constrain a widespread exploitation.</p>
<p>Replicability potential</p>	<p>During the project 500 m² pilot led to the valorisation of 75 tonnes of GLD in the production demo. At the site monitored in the first two years of the project, 3000 ton of GLD were valorised.</p>	<p>Replication: the global production of mine wastes is estimated at 15.000 – 20.000 million tons of solid waste each year. The consumption of natural resources such as soil and clay to cover this amount of material is huge which opens opportunities for GLD utilisation. Boliden operates many other mining operations where the technology can be quickly and easily replicated.</p> <p>Other alternative applications scenarios with different soil mixtures are to be evaluated.</p>

CC5 mine waste covering sealing layer based on Green Liquor Dregs, short Guidelines:

✚ The Circular Economy Model CC5 is focused on the construction of sealing layers based on mixing of Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs,) originated at the PPI industry and local glacial soils (tills) at Sweden. It supposes a greener alternative to sealing natural materials such as bentonites, enabling the valorisation GLDs, landfilled at present. Challenges come from providing enough and regular quantities of homogeneous and similar quality GLD and soil for mixture, constrained workability window (material humidity, homogeneous mixing, suitable dry weather conditions), environmental monitoring and process standardization. Construction equipment adaptation and new worker skills are required, but not very high investment is required. Lack of GLD use standards in Sweden and EU in construction applications are barriers to overcome. In addition, long-term technical and environmental performance need to be totally proven on ongoing years to overcome initial reticence from end-users and public to use GLD waste as base for construction material. Replicability of this CC5 can be suitable in Sweden and other EU countries.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Five Circular Economy Models have been shown in the present document:

CC1a Construction manufacturing: Filler aggregate (lime ash) in pre-cast Concrete

CC1b Construction manufacturing: Fillers and fine aggregates (GLDs and Grits) in asphalt pavements.

CC2 Transport Infrastructures Road Sector: Hydraulic Road Binder applications (WPFA)

CC3 Transport Infrastructures Railway Sector: Slope stabilization Gabion walls back-fill construction material (DPA+DPS →MUDIPEL®).

CC4 Chemical industry: improved cellulose, Ethanol derivatives and Ethyl Chloride production as raw material for Bermocoll (Fiber sludge)

CC5 Mining Industry: Mine waste sealing layer for mine reclamation (GLDs+fill soils)

Through this D7.3 "Guidelines for the implementation of the Circular Economy models") for the **5 Circular Economy Models developed in the PAPERCHAIN project**, the main outcomes obtained from the study of the PAPERCHAIN cases demonstrations are summarized in several Case by Case descriptions, and CEM key factors and lessons learnt during the project are attached. All this information comprises a fact sheet document that form the Guidelines for each Circular Case.

The Guidelines are intended to facilitate PAPERCHAIN CEM and be a valuable tool to quickly understand and assess for the public its potential replicability in scenarios other than those developed in PAPERCHAIN. They have been developed with a special focus on allowing the potential future replication of these circular economy models across EU in similar scenarios. Aspects such as regulation, standards, certification, and regional aspects, already studied in the project, have been considered for its elaboration. The scope of the guidelines, in any case, is limited to the output obtained in previous tasks of the project, confidentiality of the data, and general scenarios. Moreover, it pretends to serve as a starting reference for PAPERCHAIN CEM replication across EU. In addition, CEM are sufficiently explained in other public documents.

The applied methodology consisted of a deep and holistic analysis of all the available information collected during the Project (deliverables, consulting pilot participants, etc.). Most relevant key factors showed for each case were the following:

- Waste
- Regulatory framework

- Proceedings
- Barriers
- Enablers
- LCA/CO2 footprint
- Exploitation
- Replicability potential

Then, Case by Case fact sheet was completed (Chapter 3). Among the major conclusions for each case analysis, the following can be summarized: **CC1a: Lime ash Concrete Pre-casts**: lime ash can be employed successfully in the fabrication of pre-cast concrete replacing 100% of natural fillers. Technical and environmental performance achieved user requirements. CC1a CEM has a high replicability potential. "Business as usual" can be applied to this Circular Case.

CC1b: GLDs and Grits in Asphalt pavements: GLDs and Grits can replace partially standard fillers and aggregates in the production of asphalt pavements. The novel process using such wastes, nevertheless, requires from waste pre-treatment consisting on drying, sieving, and, potentially in some waste streams, also salts washing. Technical and environmental performance achieved user requirements. CC1b CEM has a high replicability potential.

CC2: Wastepaper Fly ash (WPFA) for Hydraulic Road Binders (HRBs) production: WPFA can replace standard binder in the elaboration of stabilized soils and cement-soil layers for road construction. Technical and environmental performance achieved user requirements. The process must be adapted to the characteristics of WPFA to avoid problems of mixing-compaction and generation of dust when mixing on site (stabilized soils approach). Aspects related to ashes low density must be taken in consideration for designing transportation plan and calculating the overall costs and CO₂ footprint. WPFA quality monitoring is focused on its salts and heavy metals content and variability. CC2 CEM has a high replicability potential. A technical Conformity (TC) document for its certification as product is being elaborated at present by ACCIONA with the support of TECNALIA. CC2 CEM has a high replicability potential. Such TC documents are Technical Approval Assessments issued by TECNALIA, which are proof of compliance with CTE requirements and other national regulations (RIPCI, PG3...). TCs are included in the Spanish Technical Building Code (CTE) Register as documents that facilitates the implementation of innovation in Construction and can be found also through this link: <https://www.tecnalia.com/en/lab-services/tc-issued-technical-conformity>. However, the final certification for this CC is not ready yet and thus, it is not available so far, since its completion was not foreseen within the scope and timeline of the project.

CC3: Deinking ash and sludge use in MUDIPEL® back-fill material production: MUDIPEL®, a novel material based on Deinking Paper Ash (DPA) and Deinking Paper Sludge (DPS) can be a suitable back-fill material for gabions / retaining walls construction in slope stabilization in near railways. Performance achieved user requirements. Process has some

critical points as obtaining proper wastes mixing and homogenization, humidity control and compaction on site. Environmental monitoring extra efforts are necessary for the moment until process is standardized. This light material could be employed in other construction applications (roads, mining restoration, etc.). CC3 CEM has a high replicability potential. For the moment STS approval grants the use of MUDIPEL® in Slovenia.

CC4: Chemicals production based on fiber sludge: improved cellulose, ethanol derivatives and ethyl chloride can be obtained by several chemical processes transforming the PPI rejected fibre sludge waste. The mentioned chemical products can be employed in several applications, as additives for painting products as Bermocoll®. The performance in this case achieved user requirements of quality and purity of the products. Challenges in this CC4 are the scalability of the process that requires high investment, the safety and environmental constraints for bigger production plants. On the other hand, the environmental benefit avoiding fossil raw materials and achieving a lower CO₂ footprint than actual process can be high. This CC4 process is highly specific and dependent on the new target chemicals envisaged for the replication of the circular economy model.

CC5: Mining waste covering layers based on GLDs: Green liquor Dregs and local till soil mixtures can form a highly impermeable layer capable to impede mine wastes to leachate for long-term, and therefore, can serve as a material usable in mine reclamation projects. Technical and environmental performance achieved user requirements, but (very) long-term performance need to be assessed yet. Challenges are related to GLD and soil heterogeneity, material availability, transportation (CO₂ footprint involved), and waste+soil mixing and compaction. Environmental monitoring is deeply assessed. Lack of standards for GLD use as construction material. Highly specific process (till soil), with potential to be replicated in several stakeholder mine restorations and for other potential application scenarios in Sweden or out of Sweden also.